

Uncovering the Nanoscopic Humidity Ingression in Multifunctional Additivated Halide Perovskites

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Sulfur-based multifunctional additives are attractive for increasing not only the device power conversion efficiency but also the moisture stability of perovskite solar cells. The stability of the device against external and internal stress plays a pivotal role in the commercial endeavor of emerging technologies such as perovskite photovoltaics. However, the potential of sulfur-based additives remains largely unexplored for perovskite solar cell fabrication. Here, we deduce a mechanism for the local nanoscopic humidity ingression into a multifunctional additivated formamidinium loaded halide perovskites. By tuning the iodide and bromide tails of additives, we uncovered the influence of sulfur heteroatom containing ammonium salts on the photo-physical and device properties of a formamidinium-rich perovskite absorber. In addition, we excluded the process of strong water adsorption through the proton-migration mechanism, thereby significantly improving the moisture resistance of perovskite films. The high crystallinity and long lifetime decay allowed us to achieve a higher PCE of 25.14% compared to the control at 22.49%, along with improved long-term stability by retaining 99.6% of the initial PCE after 1000 hours.

Keywords: additive, stability, perovskite solar cell, adsorption, nanoscopic mapping, humidity resistance

1. Introduction

Halide perovskites have been in the mainstream research arena of photovoltaic technologies since their seminal application in thin film device fabrication. The scientific community has witnessed a rapid rise in the power conversion efficiency (PCE) of laboratory-made perovskite solar cells (PSC) with cost-effective manufacturing methods using abundant materials.^[1,2] Nevertheless, PSCs have not yet reached the point of commercialization, mainly due to long-term instability issues. To address such a challenging issue, the formulation of perovskite and their mechanistic understandings are paramount. Although the incumbent formamidinium-rich absorber ($\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{MA}_{0.1}\text{FA}_{0.85}\text{PbI}_3$) delivers record certified efficiency (certified up to 26.7%), PSC suffers from long-term instabilities due to their susceptibility towards extrinsic features (such as moisture, heat, and light) as well as intrinsic features (such as ion migration and defects).^[3-5] Strategies have been employed to improve PSC stability, including the deployment of molecular moieties inside the precursor ink (additive) or as an additional layer (passivator). These moieties entail ammonium-based salts, small organic molecules, polymers, inorganic salts, and other large organic molecules.^[6,7] After the initial doping of the A-site with small ammonium salt additives, the trend has shifted towards the use of multi-functionalized additives.^[8,9] Arguably, the sulfur element can induce strong coordination with Lead (Pb) due to its empty outer orbital.^[10,11] Additionally, the high electronegativity of sulfur leads to a low energy barrier of phase transition which is beneficial for absorbers like CsPbI_3 , and FAPbI_3 .^[12] Chloride-based additives such as methylammonium chloride (MACl) are used to slow down the crystallization rate, allowing the grain size to be increased. Recently, multifunctional sulfur-based additives, including thiophene derivatives, thiourea, and thiocyanate derivatives, have been employed in PSCs to improve efficiency and stability.^[12-15] Our group proposed for the first time a rational additivization strategy to augment the long-term water and humidity stability of the pure formamidinium lead triiodide (FAPbI_3) layer by multifunctional ammonium salt with a sulfur heteroatom.^[16] The induced Pb-S interaction and manipulated crystallization growth are responsible for the decorated stability. Moisture-assisted perovskite degradation mechanisms were proposed including surface adsorption of water molecules, proton migration with perovskite ammonium ends, and oxygen-assisted water uptake on the perovskite surface.^[16,17] Nevertheless, the potential of sulfur-based multifunctional additives is less explored than others for reliable PSC fabrication.

Here, we uncover the impact of the S-(2-Aminoethyl)isothiuronium iodide hydroiodide and hydrobromide as additives to induce the synergistic benefits of both the ammonium ends and

the sulfur heteroatom. Using real-time and nanoscopic monitoring techniques including transmission IR characterization, we deduced that it is moisture adsorption rather than proton migration at the perovskite surface that contributes to perovskite degradation. The additives could impart a higher barrier to the adsorption of water molecules. The additivated PSC registered an efficiency of 25.14% compared to 22.49% of its control counterpart and showed boosted long-term stability over 1000 hours (with high retention >99.6%).

2. Result and Discussions

2.1. Photovoltaic performance

We fabricated PSCs with a structure of F-doped tin oxide (FTO)/compact titanium dioxide/mesoporous TiO₂/perovskite/2,2',7,7'-tetrakis(*N,N*-di(4-methoxyphenyl) amino)-9,9-spirobifluorene (spiro-OMeTAD)/Au (Scheme 1). We opted for the high-performance FA-rich triple-cation perovskite (Cs_{0.05}MA_{0.05}FA_{0.9}PbI₃) as a control sample and two additives containing sulfur heteroatoms and ammonium ends were added into the precursor solution. To incorporate the halide effects, we chose both the Iodide- and Bromide-versions of the additive (denoted as ISO-I and ISO-Br, **Figure 1a**). The detailed fabrication procedures are given in the experimental section. **Figure 1b** presents the current density-voltage (*J-V*) curves of the control, ISO-I and ISO-Br treated PSCs with photovoltaic parameters. The PSC treated with ISO-I additive showed a PCE of 24.04% with a short-circuit current density (*J*_{SC}) of 25.67 mA·cm⁻², an open-circuit voltage (*V*_{OC}) of 1141 mV, and an *FF* of 82%. The PSC treated with ISO-Br additive showed a PCE of 25.14% with a *J*_{SC} of 25.88 mA·cm⁻², a *V*_{OC} of 1165 mV, and an *FF* of 83%. The PCE of the control PSC attained a PCE of 22.49% with a *J*_{SC} of 25.16 mA·cm⁻², a *V*_{OC} of 1115 mV, and an *FF* of 80%. Tables S1 and S2 give their photovoltaic parameters. In addition, 20 devices for each configuration were prepared for statistical purposes (Fig. S1). In addition, to measure the veracity of the *J*_{SC} of the *J-V* curves we calculated the integrated *J*_{SC} from the incident photon to current efficiency (IPCE) measurements (**Figure 1c**) over the spectral range from 300 – 900 nm. The integrated *J*_{SC} for the control, ISO-I, and ISO-Br based PSCs reached 24.85, 25.47, and 25.63 mA cm⁻², which is close to the short-circuit current density (*J*_{SC}) value from the *J-V* curves with a slight loss of <5%. Furthermore, we tracked the long-term stability of fabricated PSCs under 1-sun illumination at 50 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere (**Figure 1d**) and found that the ISO-Br preserved 99.6% and the ISO-I preserved 93.2% of their initial performance after 1000 hours whereas the control device only preserved a value of 82.4%. Since the ionic radius of Br in ISO-Br (~1.96 Å) is smaller than that of I in

ISO-I (~2.20 Å), Br can enter into the perovskite lattice, thereby reducing lattice distortions, improving the perovskite crystal structure, and lowering the defect state density. Compared with ISO-I, the Br atoms in ISO-Br can also passivate the uncoordinated Pb²⁺ defects in the perovskite, and this in turn improves the quality of the perovskite layer, accelerates carrier migration, and pushes the photovoltaic performance. ISO-Br induces lattice contraction of the perovskites and improves the crystallinity of the active layer, while surface passivation by ISO organic cations increases the moisture resistance of the perovskites, thereby further improving the stability of the PSCs.

Figure 1. a) The molecular structure of additives used, b) The J - V curves, c) IPCE curves of the control PSC device, ISO-I (1.5 wt.%) treated, and ISO-Br (2.0 wt.%) treated PSC devices (active area of 0.06 cm²), and d) the maximum power point tracking of the devices under 1-sun illumination at 50 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere.

2.2 Structural and Photo-physical Characterization

Compared to the thin film of control perovskite, the relative intensity of the diffraction peak at 12.6° (associated with the PbI₂ peak) significantly decreases in the thin films treated with ISO-Br and ISO-I (Fig. S2). In addition, the average grain sizes of the control, ISO-I, and ISO-Br modified perovskite samples were 534, 687, and 915 nm, respectively (Fig. S3). This suggests that the perovskite films treated with ISO-Br and ISO-I have higher crystallinity than the control perovskite film. Next, we investigated the photophysics of thin film to gain insight into the influence of additives on PSC performance. It is a known fact that the loss in PSC performance and perovskite degradation largely occur at grain boundaries and interfaces and this accelerates when they are under external stresses. Notably, **Figure 2a** shows that the steady-state

photoluminescence (PL) intensity of the perovskite films on glass increased by ~100% with ISO-Br and ~60% with ISO-I. This suggests the effective suppression of non-radiative recombination by additives. ISO-Br and ISO-I treatments both result in increased PL (reduced nonradiative losses) and augmented PSC performance. We also performed time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) measurements on the perovskite thin films, and the transient photoluminescence intensity decay curves further support our hypothesis that thin films treated with ISO-Br and ISO-I show improved optoelectronic properties with lower non-radiative recombination. The radiation recombination lifetime can be deduced by fitting the TRPL decay (**Figure 2b**) with an exponential decay function, which is 414.7 ns for the ISO-I modified perovskite films. This is much longer than the control perovskite thin films (200.2 ns). The ISO-Br modified perovskite thin films showed a substantially extended lifetime of 627.9 ns, suggesting reduced defect density (Figure 2b). This higher PL emission intensity and longer PL lifetime values suggest the suppressed non-radiative recombination for the ISO-I and ISO-Br modified perovskite thin films.

Furthermore, we performed the femtosecond-transient absorption spectra (fs-TAS) experiments to derive the dynamics of the photogenerated charge carrier and the time constants of the various physical processes for the control, ISO-I and ISO-Br modified perovskite. The perovskite thin films were spin-coated on quartz substrates and annealed at 150 °C for 30 min. We applied a low excitation energy density of approximately $0.70 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ to prevent Auger recombination. The excitation energy density remained constant for all samples with similar thicknesses to ensure the generation of a comparable charge carrier density. The samples were probed at several pump-probe delay times with a white light continuum probe pulse using a pump excitation wavelength of 500 nm. The TAS spectra of the control, ISO-I, and ISO-Br modified perovskite thin films at representative time delays from 0.4 ps to 1 ns are displayed (Fig. S4). **Figure 2c-e** presents the fs-TAS spectra with a delay time from 0.1 ps to 1 ns. Three distinct spectral regions can be detected in all three samples,^[18-20] *i.e.*, one negative and two positive bands appeared on both sides of the negative band. The negative band is produced from ground state bleaching (GSB) while the broad and slow rise positive bands at 670-720 and fast decay broad-band at 800-830 nm stem from the absorption of excited states. The negative feature at ~776 nm (the position of the maximum absorption peak of the excitons) indicates a transient bleaching of the band edge transition which occurs due to band filling of the photoexcited charge carriers, the excitons, or both.^[20]

The positive excited state absorption (ESA) bands are formed due to newly state-filling excited-state carriers to higher energy levels transitions. An additional small transient bleaching band is present at ~ 790 nm which is assigned to the laser-induced fluorescence.^[21] Meanwhile, an ultrafast rise of the bleach was deduced in the short delay time (<1 ps). Here, a large bleaching feature implies an excited state being filled by photogenerated excitons and charge carriers. The maximum increase in ground state bleach was noted for ISO-Br additivated thin films, indicating a rapid filling of the states. We further analyzed the kinetic of the TAS spectra at different probe wavelengths to decipher different processes at different time scales. **Figure 2f** displays the temporal evolution of the absorbance measured at 764 nm of the control, ISO-I, and ISO-Br modified perovskite thin films upon pulsed laser excitation at 500 nm. The transient bleach kinetics curves are fitted with a tri-exponential function, which is associated with two faster processes (τ_1 , τ_2) and a slower process (τ_3). The slower process is related to the excitonic or carrier recombination and is tabulated (Table S3). Figure S5 further shows transient absorbance traces recorded at 710 nm and 821 nm. The first fast component in all samples is in hundreds of femtoseconds which can be ascribed to the hot carrier cooling *via* phonon scattering.²² Thus, the decay time constant (τ_1) for the fastest process is related to the carrier thermalization lifetime, which decreases from 1.49 ps for the control to 0.574 ps for the ISO-I treated and further decreases to 0.507 ps for the ISO-Br additivated thin films. The second time constant (τ_2) is attributed to the charge carrier trapping at the perovskite grain boundaries or defect recombination.^[23] The control perovskite exhibits a decay time constant (τ_2) of 28.31 ps, which increases to 105.75 ps for the ISO-I additivated perovskite thin films and to 620.109 ps for the ISO-Br additivated perovskite thin films. This increase in decay time (τ_2) to the reduction in the trap density arises from the additivization which slows down the rate of carrier recombination and thus suppresses the non-radiative recombination losses and improves the V_{oc} and fill factor. The longest time constant (τ_3) represents the carrier lifetime, which increased from 2.32 ns for the control to 4.44 ns for the ISO-Br additivated perovskite thin films. The ISO-I provides the perovskite surface with exceptional water and moisture resistance when used as an additive.^[16] We further undertook Kelvin probe force microscopy (KPFM) and scanning force microscopy (SFM) analyses to understand the water and humidity resistance at the nanoscopic level, *i.e.*, in grains and at grain boundaries. We measured the topography and contact potential difference (CPD) between a conductive tip and the surface of a sample using SFM and KPFM to determine changes on a nanometer scale.

Figure 2. a) Steady-state photoluminescence, b) time-resolved photoluminescence curve. Femtosecond-Transient absorption spectra probed at an early delay time from 0.1 to 1000 ps for c) the control perovskite, d) the ISO-I, and e) ISO-Br additivated perovskites. The samples were excited with a laser pulse at 500 nm (2.48 eV) with a fluence of $0.7 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$. f) The kinetic delay for photobleaching probed at 764 nm of three perovskite samples. The inset shows the kinetics at a short time delay (~ 5 ps).

For comparison purposes, we investigated three different half-cells before and after exposure to a high relative humidity (RH) of 85%. First, in the Ar-filled glove box, each half-cell was marked with a scratch in the center of the sample (**Figure 3a**).

This scratch indicates the surface position where we perform SFM measurements. Second, we installed the half-cells on the SFM holder. Third, after SFM imaging, we transferred the half-cells to a humidity chamber for humidity resistance testing.^[24] Fourth, after exposure to humidity, we transferred the half-cells back into the glove box for SFM analysis. All SFM measurements showed the same area of the sample before and after exposure to 85% RH for 24 hours. For the SFM we used different tips, resulting in slightly different work functions (WF). Therefore, we measured the CPD signal of each tip before and after the measurement relative to a freshly cleaved highly ordered pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) surface.^[25] The latter allows us to calculate the WF of the half-cell surfaces (Fig. S6). The topography analysis reveals that particles grew or emerged on the surface of the control after humidity exposure. We observed the growth of small particles on the control half-cell surface (**Figure 3b**). We ascribed this topography change originated from irreversible hydration and chemical reactions between

water and the surface of the samples. For the ISO-Br treated perovskite half-cell surface, most particles' topography remained unchanged, while some particles degraded to the aggregation of small particles (Figure 3d). The ISO-I treated perovskite films remained almost unchanged (**Figure 3f**). The WF of surfaces is influenced by composition, electronic states, energy band-bending, charge trapping, and surface reconstruction.^[26] For the ISO-I treated perovskites, the distribution of WF is more homogeneous compared to the control and ISO-Br treated half-cell surfaces (**Figure 3c, e, and g**).

Since different regions have different crystallization properties, we randomly selected three distinct regions on each sample to reflect the degradation conditions of the whole sample. The error bars show the variation of roughness and CPDs (**Figure 3h and 3i**). To quantify changes in topography and WF, we calculated the average roughness and WF of all samples. The roughness of the control perovskite surface increased from 23.1 nm to 27.9 nm after exposure to humidity (Figure 3h). The roughness of the ISO-Br treated perovskite thin films increased slightly from 26.5 nm to 28.2 nm while the roughness of the ISO-I treated perovskite thin film surface decreased slightly from 23.4 nm to 19.1 nm. The change in WF attests to the humidity stability of ISO-I surfaces (Figure 3i). Here the color scale bar for the WF is valid for both measurements. The WF of the control decreased by 0.8 eV from 4.6 to 3.8 eV, and the WF of ISO-Br cells decreased by 0.4 eV from 4.3 to 3.9 eV. In contrast, the ISO-I surfaces remain more stable at a WF of around 4.2 to 4.1 eV. We further compared the UV-visible spectra of the three samples before and after the humidity exposure (Fig. S7), which corroborates these results. Similar to the above topographic and WF studies, the control sample showed a drastic change in the absorption spectra indicating the perovskite degradation. Both the ISO-Br and ISO-I treated perovskite thin films displayed relatively little shifting, after the humidity exposure, indicating their enhanced humidity-repellent nature. It should be noted that this analysis reflects changes in a half-cell, *i.e.* the perovskite surface is directly exposed to humidity. Therefore, interface changes of a complete solar cell could be different from the surface changes of a half-cell.

Figure 3. Kelvin Probe Force Microscopy analyses. a) Sketch illustrating the exchange of samples between the glove box and the humidity chamber. Topography (b, d, f) and the calculated work function of the control (c), ISO-Br treated (e), and ISO-I (g) treated perovskite half-cells before and after exposure to 85% humidity for 24 hours. Roughness (h) and work function changes (i) of the control, ISO-Br, and ISO-I samples before and after humidity exposure and their error bars.

2.3 Proton migration analysis

When a perovskite surface interacts with water molecules through contact with a humid environment, surface adsorption of water molecules may lead to degradation of the perovskite architecture. Here, the uptake of water molecules is monitored using a quantitative approach exploiting H/D exchange upon exposure of hybrid perovskites to D₂O. The exchange can be conveniently followed by transmission infrared (IR) spectroscopy to probe the impact of substrate modification on the isotope exchange. The samples were exposed to the 43% RH for 5-6 days and the IR spectra were monitored in real time. The spectral variations during the H/D exchange of the ISO-Br additivated Cs_{0.05}MA_{0.05}FA_{0.9}PbI₃ sample (**Figure 4a**) are shown for the 1800-1300 cm⁻¹ region. These can be decomposed into contributions arising from the presence of FA and ISO-Br additives. At $t = 0$ h, the IR spectrum exhibits five main bands at 1712, 1636, 1613, 1469, and 1352 cm⁻¹. The intense and medium bands at 1712 and 1352 cm⁻¹ are coupled modes involving ν CN, δ NH₂, and δ CH vibrations of FA. The 1712 cm⁻¹ mode is dominated by the ν CN (50%) and δ NH₂ (40%) components, whereas the 1352 cm⁻¹ mode is dominated by the δ CH (72%) component. The 1636 and 1613 cm⁻¹ modes are instead pure δ NH₂ vibration assigned to the ISO-Br and FA species, respectively. Finally, the 1469 cm⁻¹ band is assigned to the δ NH₃⁺ mode of MA and ISO-Br. The appearance of the bands at 1636 and 1469 cm⁻¹ confirms the presence of the additive in the sample. Upon exposure to D₂O, the intensity of the 1712 and 1352 cm⁻¹ bands gradually decreases in favor of 1681 and 1337 cm⁻¹ bands, respectively. Simultaneously, the decrease of the δ NH₂ band at 1613 cm⁻¹ mode is associated with the increase of the δ ND₂ band at 1394 cm⁻¹ (Figure 4a). A weak band is also noted at ca. 1490 cm⁻¹, assigned to the δ NHD mode of FA (band at 1496 cm⁻¹) and to that of ISO-Br (band at 1482 cm⁻¹). The latter is slightly shifted in energy due to the presence of the longer alkyl chain. Delving into the spectral variation of this band can give valuable information on the H/D exchange for the different organic species (MA, FA, and ISO-Br) in the sample. In a previous report,^[27] the H/D exchange for the FAPbI₃ was followed by summing the contributions from the vibrational bands related to the coupled modes involving ν CN, δ NH₂, and δ CH vibrations.

The overall rate of H/D exchange in hybrid perovskites is dependent on the content of water vapor in contact with the sample surface (relative humidity, RH), the presence of surface protective barriers towards moisture, the size of the sample grains, and the intrinsic diffusion rates of H⁺ and D⁺ inside the material.^[28] **Figure 4b** compares the H/D exchange process for Cs_{0.05}MA_{0.05}FA_{0.9}PbI₃, and with samples treated using ISO-Br and ISO-I analyzed according to

a diffusion model based on the presence of spherical particles.^[29,30] Focusing on the initial exchange rate ($t \leq 10^4$ s) shows that the exchange rate of the ISO-Br sample is intermediate to that of the ISO-I doped sample (slowest) and that of the reference sample (fastest), in agreement with the relative propensity towards water damage evidenced from SFM analysis of the samples exposed to water vapor (Fig. S6). The vibrational bands in the samples can be assigned to contributions from the bulk FA and the ISO-Br or ISO-I additives. This allows independent monitoring of the H/D exchange for the functional molecules separately from that of the bulk sample. However, as the additive molecules are only present in a small amount ($< 2\%$), precise kinetic analysis of the H/D exchange for these species is limited by the signal-to-noise ratio. Nevertheless, it can be deduced that for the FA group of the ISO-Br and ISO-I additive, the exchange is complete after *ca.* 5 hours compared to > 100 hours for the bulk FA species (**Figure 4c**). Considering that each molecular species undergoing H/D exchange will witness similar intrinsic diffusion rates of H^+ and D^+ inside the sample, arguably all the species exhibit identical or very similar exchange rates. On the contrary, for the dopant *vs.* the bulk FA evidence that the dopant is localized in a different environment than the majority of the bulk sample. An apparent possibility is the dopant is mainly located at the grain boundaries. However, this can entail a rapid H/D exchange suggesting faster completion than the time resolution of the experiment. The SEM images of the additivated samples reveal the presence of small semi-crystalline grains with a size of only a few tens to one hundred nm (Fig. S3c). This suggests that the dopants are predominantly located in these smaller grains which will undergo significantly faster H/D exchange due to the smaller grain size. Moreover, the energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) mapping shows that the distribution of sulfur atoms is uniform, indicating that ISO-Br covers the entire perovskite thin film (Fig. S8). Arguably, it excludes a smaller portion of the additives present inside the larger grains or in the interstitial region between grains.

To study the resistance of ISO-Br to water, we further calculated the activation energy for water molecules penetrating the perovskite surface (Fig. S9). The activation energy for the diffusion of water molecules on the control perovskite surface is about 0.22 eV after relaxation, which increases to 0.41 eV with the additivization of ISO-Br molecules. The increased activation energy is attributed to the formation of Pb-S bonds among them,^[16] suggesting the enhanced surface water resistance for perovskite films. Furthermore, we ran the molecular dynamic (MD) simulation for the material-water interface at 300 K for 10 ps with a step size of 1 fs to uncover the adsorption-permeation process of water molecules on the perovskite surface. The stable (100) surface for $FAPbI_3$ was chosen to study the adsorption and diffusion behaviors of water

molecules. The perovskite surface is severely eroded by water after 10 ps of relaxation, with a large number of water molecules entering the perovskite lattice, while only a small number of water molecules penetrate the perovskite lattice after 10 ps of relaxation, presumably due to the hydrophobicity of the ISO-Br molecule (Fig. S10). This mitigates water erosion effectively and ensures the long-term operational stability of the device.

Figure 4. Proton diffusion study. a) IR spectra of ISO-Br treated $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{MA}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{PbI}_3$ film before ($t = 0$ h, black line) and after ($t = 124$ h, red line) exposition to 43% relative humidity of D_2O . b) Relative H/D composition ($m(t)$) for thin films of the control (black), ISO-Br treated (red), and ISO-I treated (blue) $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{MA}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{PbI}_3$ samples exposed to D_2O vapor (RH = 43%) at room temperature. The inset shows changes at short exposure times with solid lines obtained from best fits according to a diffusion model.^[31] IR spectra of the bands assigned to the δNHD stretching modes of c) the ISO-Br and d) ISO-I treated $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{MA}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{PbI}_3$ films exposed to D_2O (RH = 43%).

3. Conclusion

We probed the impact of multifunctional additives containing sulfur on the stabilization of the perovskite layer at the nanoscopic level. The improved resistance towards damage by water stems from the inclusion of small amounts of diammonium additives. ISO-Br and ISO-I appear to be unrelated to the diffusivity of protons within the material and show similar exchange rates. This further attests to the role of surface water adsorption in humidity-repellent perovskite surfaces. We also observe that the signal for the additive undergoes a faster H/D exchange than the bulk FA, suggesting that the additive is included in smaller grains and is not fully expelled toward the grain boundaries where the exchange would be too fast to monitor. The additives arguably contribute to strengthening the crystal lattice of the perovskite grains, which reduces their propensity toward undergoing irreversible conversion to PbI_2 . Our developed methodology with heteroatomic additivization strategy not only achieves high intrinsic stability for formamidinium-enriched thin films but also pushes the performance of the devices from 22.49 to 25.14%.

4. Experimental Section

The details of thin-film characterization, device fabrication, and simulation studies are described in Supporting Information.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

This work received funding from the European Union H2020 Programme under a European Research Council Consolidator grant [MOLEMAT, 726360], National Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 22379049), China Postdoctoral Science Foundation (Grant No. 2022M711236). Support from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation INTERACTION {PID2021-129085OB-I00}) and CNS2022-136171 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the “European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR” as well as by the French ANR (ANR-18-CE05-0021-01) and the Region Nouvelle Aquitaine (STRIPE project no. 2019-1R1M08) is also acknowledged. X.S. acknowledges support by CSC (contract 202204910093). We acknowledge Franjo Weber for his support in performing KPFM measurements. We would like to thank SGIker facilities of the University of Basque Country.

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